

ISOQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES AS POSSIBLE AMOEBACIDES. PART II

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The Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation of malondi- β -phenethylamide with P_2O_5 has led to the formation of a mixture of (I) and (II). The constitutions of (I), its dehydrogenated product (III) and of (II) have been discussed in the light of their ultraviolet absorption spectra.

It has been recorded in Part I (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 699) that malondi- β -phenethylamide undergoes the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation in presence of P_2O_5 to yield 1:1'-methylene-bis-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (I). Repetition of the reaction with a larger quantity of the amide has now led to the isolation, besides (I), of another basic compound in poor yield, which, on elemental analyses, appears to be 1-(*N*- β -phenethylacetamido)-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (II). The constitution of (II) has been established by conversion, with P_2O_5 , into (I).

The striking feature of the compound (I) is its fine yellow colour, which is further deepened by hydrogen chloride absorption in ethanolic solution. It has been recorded (Part I, *loc. cit.*) that dehydrogenation of (I) over Pd—C leads to the formation of the fully aromatised isoquinoline (III) as a cream-coloured solid, but the colour is now found to remain unaffected by hydrogen chloride absorption in ethanolic solution. These observations tend to suggest the presence of conjugation in the compound (I). In order to establish this point, the absorption spectra of (I), its dehydrogenated product (III) and of (II) have been studied. It is found that, whereas the absorption spectrum of (III) (Fig. B) and that of (II) (Fig. C) resemble those of normal isoquinoline derivatives, e.g., 1-methyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline and 1-benzyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (cf. Bills and Noller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 957), the absorption spectra (Fig. A) of (I) in ethanolic solution and in normal ethanolic hydrogen chloride solution present quite a different picture. The latter indicate the presence of conjugation in (I), both in ethanolic as well as in

FIG. A

U. V. spectrum of (I) (0.001072% solution).

ethanolic hydrogen chloride solutions, brought about by a double bond, exocyclic to the isoquinoline ring. But as the intensity of absorption is greater, in the present case, in ethanolic hydrogen chloride solution than in ethanolic solution, it is considered that the base (I) in ethanolic hydrogen chloride may exist in the form (IV) and the same in ethanolic solution exists as an equilibrium mixture of (I) and (IV).

FIG. B

U. V. spectrum of (III) (0.00134% solution).

FIG. C

U. V. spectrum of (II) in ethanol (0.000939% solution).

In the literature 1-(α -picolyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (V) (Clemo *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 610), which is structurally related to (I), is being found to show characteristics comparable to those of (I). On the basis of ultraviolet absorption spectrum, Bills and Noller (*loc. cit.*) have adduced evidence to show that the yellow colour of this α -picolyloisoquinoline derivative is due to conjugation between the two aromatic rings. In other words, the base (V) exists in the form: 1-(α -picolal)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (VI).

EXPERIMENTAL

Action of P₂O₅ on Malondi-β-phenethylamide : Formation of 1'-Methylene-bis-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (I) and 1-(N-β-phenethylacetamido)-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (II).—A mixture of malondi-β-phenethylamide (32 g.) and P₂O₅ (128 g.) in anhydrous toluene (640 c.c.) was refluxed under mechanical stirring in an oil-bath for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled in ice and treated with ice-water. The aqueous layer was separated, washed with ether and filtered. The filtrate, on basification with NaOH, furnished a pasty solid which was purified by acid-alkali treatment. The pasty solid (11.3 g.), dried *in vacuo* over H₂SO₄ (conc.), was triturated with warm benzene and the insoluble portion* was filtered.

The filtrate was evaporated on the steam-bath, when a dark pasty mass was obtained. On trituration with ethanol, a fine yellow solid (3.4 g.) was obtained, which, on crystallisation with ethanol, was found to be (I) (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*).

The solid* (II, 1.6 g.) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 160-61°. It was dried *in vacuo* over P₂O₅ at 100°. (Found: C, 78.34; H, 6.72; N, 9.18. C₁₅H₂₀ON₂ requires C, 78.08; H, 6.85; N, 9.59%). It is readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated by alkali. When treated with P₂O₅ under conditions as employed above, it was converted into (I).

Absorption Spectra.—For the determination of absorption spectra, the compounds were dissolved in ethanol suitable for UV studies. The dilution was made with an "Agla" brand Micrometer Syringe (B & W) using ethanol or ethanolic hydrogen chloride as the case may be. The readings were taken in a Beckman model DU spectrophotometer provided with 1 cm silica cells.

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